

GRASSCUTTER CULTIVATION AND USES: ISSUES AND CHALLENGES. A STUDY OF
SELECTED LOCAL GOVERNMENT AREAS IN EDO STATE, NIGERIA.

¹Bello, Y.O, ¹Bello, M.B and ²Iwanegbe, I.

¹Department of Hospitality Management, Auchu Polytechnic, Auchu Edo State, Nigeria, ²Department of Food Technology, Auchu Polytechnic, Auchu, Edo State, Nigeria

ABSTRACT

The survey was carried out to determine the challenges facing the production and uses of grasscutter in Edo state with special emphasis on selected local government areas in the state. A four stage stratified sampling methods were adopted to determine the sample unit as well as the sample size of the studied population (Edo State). Simple percentage and ANOVA were used for the analysis. The result shows that about 90% of the respondents were aware of the existence of grasscutter. Also, about 83.33% of the respondents are not aware of other uses of grasscutter apart from being a source of meat to man. The research further shows that 66.67% of the respondents are not willing to invest in grasscutter farming even if empowered. Also about 8.34% of the respondents may wish to invest on grasscutter farming but attributed their challenge to lack of production knowledge. The result further shows that ignorance is the major reason Edo citizens may not want to invest on grasscutter production. Mass enlightens on the socio-economic importance of grasscutter should be done to educate Nigerians and more so Edo citizens on the various value of grasscutter. Government of Edo State through the ministry of agriculture should collaborate with foreign and local experts on grasscutter cultivation to educate and assists willing Nigerians and Edo citizens on scientific and modern approach to grasscutter cultivation.

KEY WORDS: - *Grasscutter, Consumption, Production, Investment*

INTRODUCTION

Based on rapid growth in human population in the developing countries, accessibility to animal protein is very low and unable to meet demand. Wildlife species production in form of domestication should therefore be encouraged as a possible means to bridging accessibility of animal based protein gap. It is pertinent to affirm the fact that government of developing countries in attempt to achieve this objective has encouraged mass domestication of grasscutter and other wild animals to take advantage of their social- economic values. Grasscutter is a small bush animal, cheap to produce than most other traditional livestock and whose meat is more valuable and appreciated by the local population in Africa. (Respect e-Zine, 2006). People in the region of Africa do traditionally captured grasscutters and raised them at home for personal consumption. Aware of the potential of a more widespread domestic creation of the animal, some countries are already encouraging their farmers to raise grasscutter as backyard livestock. Bello and Bello (2010) affirmed this fact by pointing that the demand for grasscutter meat is large in the region, and it is not currently being met. Hence markets for it already exists very much in Africa, and it often sells more than chicken, beef, pork and lamb.

The problem essentially is that despite the food and economic value of grasscutter, its cultivation and uses in Nigeria and indeed in Edo state had not being encouraging. Hence, the reasons for this research work, to examine the Nigerians attitude towards the cultivation and uses of grasscutter.

ORIGIN AND PHYSICAL FEATURES OF GRASSCUTTER

Grasscutter according to Asibey (1997) belongs to the order rodent and family *Thryonomidae* which contains only genus *Thryonomys*. Dorst and Dandelele (1999) recognized only two species which they described as greater grasscutter, *Thryonomys swinderianus temminac* and the lesser grasscutter *Thryonomys gregorians temminac*. This rodent is widely known through Africa, South of Sahara and it is commonly referred to as grasscutter, cane-rat or cutting grass. They are heavily built, thick set animal with rounded muscle, small round ears, short tails and harsh bristly fur. They have a peculiar bristle tail which readily fractures near the base if

seized, much like the easily atomized tail of the lizard, a phenomenon that is off tremendous protective value. The coarse bristly coat has no under-fur, though under magnification some sparsely scattered extremely fine straight under-fur is visible. The overall appearance is usually dark brown, speckled with yellow or grey above butt white below. The chin and throat appear white. The head is a bit small for the size of the body. The small circular ear is covered strong and well padded and are armed with powerful straight claws. The total body length range from 35cm to 60cm and its tail length range from 7cm to 25cm. The animal has many predators including leopards, mongoose and python in addition to man. (Olayemi, 2002)

MEAT QUALITIES AND OTHER USES OF GRASSCUTTER

FMEDR (2000) explains the meat qualities of grasscutter compare favorably with those of domesticated livestock species. According to the author, the nutritional value of grasscutter meat is as good as those from domestic animals. Beef, lamb and pork also contain higher fat percentage than meat from the grasscutter. In fact grasscutter meat is nutritionally superior to domestic meat because of its high protein to fat ratio and higher mineral contents. The meat quality according to Bello *et al* (2011) is also leaner and non-cholesterogenic. The meat is very tasty when compared to both domestic and familiar game species. Igene (1992) reported that grasscutter play an important role in traditional African medicine for preparation of concoctions for fertility and so on. In Ghana, the hair of the grasscutter is used to season food just as much as it's stomach and intestinal contents. Also, the pancreas of the grasscutter contains a high concentration of insulin which is used for local preparation for the treatment of diabetes.

SOCIAL-ECONOMIC IMPORTANCE OF GRASSCUTTER

In Ghana, it has been ascertained that grasscutter contributes to both local and export earnings. Olayemi (2002) pointed that about 73 tones of the animals are sold in a year and recent surveys show that grasscutter dominates bush meat trade in Ghana. The author further affirmed that most of these quantities are traded locally as fresh or smoked form. Smoked grasscutter is exported to USA and Europe hence, becoming a source of foreign exchange earnings. The implication in this information shows that grasscutter can serve as a considerable income earner for both the small scale peri- urban or rural livestock producers.

METHODOLOGY

The research methodology adopted in this research work is a survey approach. A four stage stratified sampling were adopted to determine the sample unit and sample size of the studied population. That is, Edo State. The procedure involves acknowledging the number of local government areas in Edo State hence, a total of 18 Local Government Areas was identified. The researchers serially numbered the 18 Local Government Areas from 1-18 and automatically picked the first Local Government Area on the list while others were picked at an interval of 3 thus, about 6 Local Government Areas which includes: Etsako West, Etsako Central, Oredo, Esan West, Owan East and Akoko Edo Local Government areas were picked. In the second stage, the researchers identified the major towns and villages in each of the 6 Local Government Areas identified hence, an average of 25 towns and villages were identified in each of the Local Government Areas. Thus a total of 150 towns and villages were identified in the 6 Local Government Areas.

In stage three, all the towns identified in the 6 Local Government Areas were also serially numbered from 1-150 and the first town on the list was automatically picked while others were picked at an interval of 5. Hence, about 30 towns were picked. This implies that the sample unit was the 30 towns/villages in the 6 Local Government Areas that were picked. In stage four, the researchers administered two questionnaires each per household and about five households were covered within each street of an average of 20 streets per town. Hence, a total of 200 questionnaires were administered per town. Therefore, an average of 6000 questionnaires was administered in all the 30 towns/villages under study. Thus, the premise on which the analysis of this research work was done. Also, ANOVA is used as the statistical method to test for the hypothesis that were formulated while simple percentage is used for the analysis thus, enabling the researchers to draw inferences in the course of the work.

DATA PRESENTATION AND ANALYSIS

Table 1: Demographic Characteristics of the Respondents on the Cultivation and Uses of Grasscutter in Edo State.

Features	Responses	Percentage %
Male	3900	65
Female	2100	35
Total	6000	100
Age in year		
Above 25	3300	55
Below 25	2700	45
Total	6000	100

Source: Field Survey 2011.

From the Table 1, the respondents were made up of male (65%) and female (35%) with an average age of above 25 years (55%) and 25 years and below (45%).

Table 2: Awareness on the Existence of Grasscutter by the Citizens of Edo State.

Responses	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Agree	5400	90
Not agree	180	03
Indifference	420	07
Total	6000	100

Source: Field Survey 2011.

From the Table 2 , about 90% of the respondents attest to the knowledge of grasscutter existence. While about 03% of the respondents declined having knowledge of grasscutter existence. Also about 7% of the respondents were indifference. The index in this information shows that many Edo citizens have good knowledge of the existence of grasscutter.

Table 3: Socio- Economic Importance of Grasscutter to Edo Citizens.

Responses	Frequency	percentage (%)
Source of Meat	5000	88.33
Source of Foreign Exchange Earnings	700	11.67
Treatment of ailments	150	02.50
Indifferent	150	02.50
Total	6000	100

Source: Field Survey 2011.

Table 3 shows that about (88.33%) of the respondents attributed consumption of grasscutter to its socio-economic value. Also about 11.67% of the respondents were of the opinion that grasscutter have foreign exchange earnings value, while about 2.5% of the respondents believed that the animal can be used to treat ailments. Furthermore, about 2.5% of the respondents were indifferent. The index in this information shows that majority of Nigeria populace believed that raising grasscutter for meat is the only socio- economic value of the animal.

Table 4: Willingness of Edo Citizens to Investment in Grasscutter Farming if Empowered by the Government.

Responses	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Willing	1000	16.67
Not Willing	4000	66.66
Indifference	1000	16.67
Total	6000	100

Source: Field Survey 2011.

Table 4 shows that about 16.67% of the respondents are ready to invest in grasscutters farming if empowered by the government. Also about 66.67% of the respondents are not willing to invest in grasscutter farming even if they have the resources to do so, while about 16.67% of the respondents were indifference. The index in this information shows that citizens of Edo State will continue to depend on the natural grasscutters in the bush for consumption and for other uses against mass cultivating it due to low knowledge of its socio-economic importance.

Table 5: Reasons for not investing in Grasscutter Farming in Edo State.

Responses	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Have no economic viability	1500	25
Naturally exist in the bush	2000	33.33
Alien to African culture	2000	33.33
Lack of cultivation knowledge	500	08.34
Total	6000	100

Table 5 shows that about 25% of the respondents may not invest in grasscutter farming due to the fact that investment in grasscutter farming does not have any economic viability. While about 33.33% of the respondents affirmed that grasscutter cultivation is alien to African culture.

Also about 33.33% of the respondents believed that such investment is not necessary since the animal is naturally available in the bush. Furthermore, about 3.4% of the respondents wish to invest in grasscutter cultivation but attributed their challenge to lack of cultivation knowledge. The index in this information shows that ignorance is still the major challenge facing mass investment in grasscutter farming in Edo State.

TEST OF HYPOTHESIS

In attempt to determine the validity of the findings in this research work, the researchers formulated and tested a hypothesis as follows:

Table 6: Ignorance is a major Constraint to Grasscutter Cultivation in Edo State.

RESPONSES	LGA ₁	LGA ₂	LGA ₃	LGA ₄	LGA ₅	LGA ₆	TOTAL
Strongly agreed	400	410	390	450	710	400	
Agreed	300	290	320	250	300	350	
Disagreed	150	140	140	150	140	100	
Indifference	150	160	150	150	150	150	
$\sum X$	1000	1000	1000	1000	1000	1000	6000
Mean of \bar{x}	250	250	250	250	250	250	1500
$\sum x^2$	295000	297000	296000	310000	277850	315000	1791800

5% level of significance.

Note: LGA1,2,3,4,5, and 6 means Local Government Area 1,2,3,4,5 and 6.

Formulated Hypothesis:

Null Hypothesis (H_0) Ignorance on the socio-economic value of Grasscutter is not the major constraint to its cultivation in Edo State.

Alternative Hypothesis (H_1) Ignorance on the socio-economic value of Grasscutter is the major constraint to its cultivation in Edo state.

Sum of square calculated:

$$TSS = \sum X^2 - \frac{(\sum x)^2}{n}$$

$$= 291,800$$

$$TRSS = nx_j^2 - \frac{(\sum x^2)}{n}$$

$$= 143,906,250$$

$$ESS = TSS - TRSS$$

$$= 143,614,450$$

Mean square calculated:

$$TRMS = \frac{TRSS}{r - 1}$$

$$= 47,968,750$$

$$EMS = \frac{ESS}{n - r}$$

$$= 7,180,722.5$$

$$F_{cal} = \frac{TRMS}{EMS}$$

$$= 6.68$$

$$F_{\alpha 3, 24} 0.05 = 3.10$$

DECISION RULE

Since the value of F_{cal} falls within the reject region thus null hypothesis is rejected, while alternate hypothesis is accepted. Therefore ignorance on the socio-economic value of grasscutter is the major constraint to its cultivation in Edo state.

SUMMARY OF FINDINGS

The research shows that about 90% of the respondents attest to having a good knowledge on the existence of grasscutter, 3% decline having the knowledge while about 7% were indifferent. Hence, Nigerians and particularly, Edo State people have good knowledge about grasscutter. However on the socio-economic importance of grasscutters, about 88.33% of the respondents attributed only consumption of grasscutter to its socio-economic value. Also about 11.67% of the respondents were of the opinion that grasscutter have foreign exchange earnings value while about 2.5% of the respondents believed that the animal can be used to produce medicine for treating ailment. Furthermore, about 2.5% of the respondents were also indifferent. The research further shows that about 66.66% of the respondents are not ready to invest in grasscutter farming even if empowered. However about 16.67% of the respondents are ready to invest in the business. Reasons attributed to non investment in grasscutter farming are: the animal not having economic viability (25%), naturally existing in the bush (33.33%) and lack of knowledge of cultivation (3.34%). Finally ignorance of the people on the socio-economic value of grasscutter is identified as the major constraints to cultivating grasscutter in Edo state.

CONCLUSION

- Majority of Edo people (90%) have good knowledge on the existence of grasscutter.
- Many Edo citizens (88.33%) believed that raising grasscutter for meat consumption is the only socio-economic value of the animal.
- Majority of Edo citizens (83.33%) does not have good knowledge on other uses of grasscutter apart from using it as a source of meat.
- Many Edo dwellers (66.66%) may not want to invest in grasscutter cultivation even if empowered.
- Ignorance on the socio-economic importance of grasscutter was identified as the major reason Edo people may not want to invest in grasscutter cultivation.

RECOMMENDATIONS

- Mass enlightenment on the socio-economic importance of grasscutter should be done to educate Nigerians and more-so Edo dwellers on the value of grasscutter.
- Researchers in food related discipline should advance their research and publications effort in this area of animal cultivation and ensure that their findings are accessible to the people.
- Government of Nigeria and that of Edo State through the ministry of agriculture should partner with the foreign and local experts on grasscutter cultivation to educate willing Nigerians and more so Edo citizens on the scientific and modern approaches to cultivating grasscutter.

REFERENCES

- Asibey, E.A. (1997). Traditional Hunting in West Africa with reference to Ghana. Memco M.B. Department of Game and Wildlife. P. 41
- Bello, Y.O. and Bello, M.B. (2010). Basics of Food Production. Ondo. Grace excellent publishers.
- Bello, Y.O. Bello, M.B., Iwanegbe, I., Gladys, I. and Okoli, C.I.(2011). Contemporary Approach to Quality and Food Production. Benin Diamond Publishing House.
- Dorst, A and Dandelele, M (1999). How to Breed a Grasscutter. Ghana. Insure Concept.
- FMEDR (2000). Third National Development Plan
- Igene, J.O (1992). Food Technology National feed self- sufficiency and Agro Industrialization. The Nigeria Experience. Inaugural Lecture Series 91/92, University of Maiduguri.

Olayemi, J.K (2002). Challenges of Food Security in Nigeria. A Paper presented at a seminal on planning and management of Agriculture sector. Guarantee Food security at all times held at Cape coast university, Ghana on 12th November.

Respect e-zine (2006). Grasscutters project: Enhancing communities Together. Ghana. Refugee Education sponsorship program.

Received for Publication: 20/06/12

Accepted for Publication: 05/07/12

Corresponding author

Bello, Y.O,

Department of Hospitality Management, Auchu Polytechnic, Auchu Edo State, Nigeria